

How Queer Are Our Curricula?

Perspectives on Queer LIS Education in Germany

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Pre-Circulating Essay for “Queer Bibliography In The Making” (QB2025)

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A Queer Library Begins in the Classroom

What does it mean for a library to be queer? Is it the presence of queer literature on its shelves? The visibility of queer creators and voices in its event programme? The representation in its classification systems? These are important questions, but none of them can be fully addressed unless we first ask: Who is answering these questions, who is shaping the present and the future of libraries, and how are they being trained?

The project presented, called “Queerness in der bibliothekswissenschaftlichen Lehre” (QueerBiL), which stands for “Queerness in Library and Information Science Education”, takes a foundational assumption as its starting point: The cultivation of queer libraries begins not in acquisitions departments or programme committees, but in the classrooms where future librarians learn to think critically about knowledge systems, social responsibility, ethics, and institutional power. It is an attempt to understand – and a first step towards reshaping – Library and Information Science (LIS) education in Germany through a queer lens.

The goal is not only a stocktaking or critique of the status quo, but a constructive inquiry into what queer LIS education can look like in the future. This includes curricula, institutional as well as personal positioning, and affective relationships between students, faculty, and the communities libraries serve. The ultimate aim is to contribute to a body of LIS scholarship and practice that fully integrates queer perspectives – thereby enabling the development of queer bibliographies, queer library services, and queer professional communities.

A Structural Silence in Germany

Queerness is not a niche issue. According to a 2024 Ipsos survey, 12% of adults in Germany identify as queer (Ipsos, 2024). And yet, queer perspectives remain marginalized in LIS education, research, practice, and professional discourse in Germany (Gerlach, 2023). This absence is structural, and it is self-perpetuating. Without training, future librarians are left ill-equipped to consider queer needs in their professional roles and queer scholarship isn't pursued. Without queer-inclusive practices and queer scholarship, queer patrons remain underserved and libraries as well as librarians hesitate to take a stance. And without institutional positioning, the identification of training needs and research won't be recognised or communicated.

This is not merely an issue of inclusion, it is an issue of epistemic justice. Who gets to be seen, named, and classified in library systems? Who is at the centre in the story that libraries tell about knowledge? And who is missing – not just from the catalogue, but from the educational structures that determine how knowledge professionals are formed?

The motivation for this project is grounded in both academic and personal positioning. As a researcher embedded in the German LIS community and as a member of the Queerbrarians – a German-speaking network of queer librarians, those who are training to become librarians and all other library staff – I am aware of the silences that shape our field (Frick et al., 2024). These silences manifest in the scarcity of queer-themed LIS coursework, in the limited availability of relevant German scholarship, and in the institutional reluctance to take public stances on gender, orientation, and attraction. They are also evident in the cautious self-positioning of many librarians, who are not encouraged to bring personal perspectives into professional contexts. This project is a response to that gap – an attempt to make space for queer voices in the formation of library knowledge and practice.

From Loop to Libraries

A key conceptual model underpinning this research is the Loop Model developed by Gerlach in 2023, which articulates the interplay between (1) LIS research and practice, (2) the institutional self-understanding of libraries, and (3) the personal positioning of library professionals (Gerlach, 2023). These areas do not operate in isolation, they loop into and reinforce one another, creating the conditions under which queer topics, people, and perspectives may be recognized and legitimised within libraries and LIS.

However, one area remains underexplored in this model: education. In this project, we propose (4) LIS education as an additional area in the Loop Model that functions as a site of transformation. What is taught in LIS curricula influences how future professionals position themselves (3), how they understand and operate libraries (2), and what kinds of research and practice they pursue (1). By investigating queer perspectives within (4) LIS education, we aim to highlight, interrupt and reconfigure the broader dynamics.

Curricula as Infrastructure toward a Queer Bibliography

To speak of a “queer bibliography in the making” is to highlight the active, ongoing labor of constructing a field. Bibliographies are more than collections of literature, they are infrastructures of knowledge that encode decisions about what matters, who speaks, and what is preserved. They shape what is read, conceived, taught and learned.

But bibliographies do not emerge in isolation. They require people – readers, writers, curators – who recognize the value of queer perspectives, who seek out marginal voices, and who invest in building new discourses. In this sense, curricula precede bibliographies. They determine what is assigned and what is recognized as legitimate knowledge and practice.

The project presented therefore understands LIS education as a critical site for intervention. By mapping and amplifying queer content in LIS education, we aim to support the development of a queer bibliography. We also hope to stimulate conversations about what counts as professional knowledge and who gets to define it.

Research Questions and Methodology

The theoretical extension of the Loop Model proposed in this research project is guided by a transformative research design, which foregrounds social responsibility and seeks to effect structural change through inquiry. In this sense, the project is not only descriptive but also normative, as it aims to intervene in LIS education to make it more just, inclusive, and reflective for one of the many marginalised communities that libraries serve.

At the heart of this project are two primary research questions:

1. Where and how do queer topics, people, and perspectives appear in LIS education in Germany today?
2. Where and how can queer topics, people, and perspectives appear in LIS education and interact in Germany in the future?

In addition, we want to take a closer look at the potential interplay with the other areas of the Loop Model. To address these questions, we adopt a mixed-methods approach – specifically, an exploratory sequential design consisting of three core components:

1. Qualitative survey of educators

This phase involves an in-depth qualitative survey directed at LIS educators in Germany and German-speaking countries. It will explore their current teaching practices, attitudes towards queer topics, and personal positioning in relation to gender, orientation, and attraction. This will provide insights into both explicit curriculum content and the hidden curriculum of norms and values transmitted through teaching.

2. Systematic review of theses

The second phase focuses on identifying and analyzing LIS theses that center or touch on queer aspects of library work. This will help to trace the intersection between student learning and emerging fields of research, offering a view into how queer inquiry is being cultivated – or not – at the margins of formal curricula.

3. Quantitative survey of students

Building on the first two phases, this final step will involve a quantitative survey of current LIS students. It will explore their perceptions of current curricular content and personal positioning of educators as well as their ideas and needs for future curricula.

As a low response rate is expected for component 1, and in order to take into account practising librarians, an additional qualitative step will be included. A workshop at the largest

German library conference BiblioCon complements the research design. It aims to collect the gaps in queer education that librarians experience in practice as well as their needs. It also informs component 3.

Taken together, this research design allows for a dynamic picture of the state of queer LIS education in Germany, from both the top-down (educators) and bottom-up (students) as well as from a practitioner's point of view and through the transitional space of student research.

Preliminary Observations

Although data analysis is still ongoing, early conversations with Queerbrarians, a rapid review of published LIS theses, and initial qualitative results from the survey of educators suggest some preliminary themes:

- Minimal formal integration: Queer issues are rarely addressed explicitly in course syllabi. When they do appear, they are often in optional or elective contexts, not as core or regular components of foundational courses. They may even be raised by students rather than educators.
- Individual commitment vs. institutional support: Where queer perspectives are integrated, this often results from the personal initiative of individual educators rooted in the library mission rather than from institutional mandates. This creates an unevenness and fragility in their presence.
- Emerging scholarship: Student theses represent a growing – if still marginal – site of queer inquiry in LIS. These theses often go unnoticed beyond their institutional repositories and are rarely cited or circulated in the broader LIS discourse.

These patterns underscore the need not only for more representation, but for more institutional courage – to name queer issues as professionally relevant, and to support the educators and students who wish to engage with them.

From Reflection to Transformation

Ultimately, the aim is not simply to document absence, but to enable presence: the presence of queer themes in syllabi, the presence of queer educators and guest speakers, the presence of queer students who feel empowered to bring their full selves into their professional formation. Most importantly, we need the presence of libraries that do more than tolerate diversity – they celebrate, support, and fight for it. This requires more than content. It requires pedagogical courage, institutional commitment, and a willingness to re-imagine what LIS education can be. It requires seeing the classroom as a microcosm of the library, and the curriculum as a map of possible futures.

The project invites everyone, including those attending this conference, to consider their own positionalities and pedagogies. What area of the Loop Model are you contributing to? What bibliography are you building? And how might we, together, queer the future of LIS education?

Literature

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